

Haematological and Serum Biochemical Responses of Japanese Quails (*Coturnix Coturnix Japonica*) to Dietary Ginger (*Zingiber Officinale*) Supplementation

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ABSTRACT: The search for natural alternatives to synthetic growth promoters in poultry production has increased due to concerns over drug residues and antimicrobial resistance. Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) has been identified as a potential phyto-genic additive with immunomodulatory and health-promoting properties. This study evaluated the effects of dietary ginger powder supplementation on haematological and serum biochemical parameters of Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*). The study was conducted at the Poultry Unit of the Animal Science Livestock Teaching and Research Farm, Bayero University Kano. A total of 96 Japanese quails were randomly assigned to four dietary treatments containing 0% (control), 0.5%, 1.0%, and 1.5% ginger powder over a six-week period. Haematological parameters assessed included packed cell volume (PCV), haemoglobin (Hb), red blood cell (RBC), white blood cell (WBC), total plasma protein (TPP), and differential leukocyte counts. Serum biochemical indices evaluated were total protein, albumin, urea, creatinine, glucose, and liver enzymes (AST, ALT, and ALP).

Dietary ginger supplementation had no significant effect on erythrocytic indices, albumin, creatinine, AST, ALT, or glucose levels, indicating physiological safety across all inclusion levels. However, WBC counts increased significantly ($p < 0.05$) with higher ginger inclusion, suggesting enhanced immune response. Total serum protein and urea levels were significantly influenced, indicating improved protein utilization. Additionally, alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity was significantly elevated at 1.5% inclusion, possibly reflecting increased bone metabolic activity.

Inclusion of ginger powder up to 1.5% in the diet of Japanese quail is safe and beneficial, enhancing immune competence without adverse effects on physiological health. Ginger shows strong potential as a natural feed additive for improving poultry health and productivity.

KEYWORDS: Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*), haematological parameters, serum biochemical indices.

1. INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) has emerged as a valuable model in poultry production and research due to its rapid growth rate, early sexual maturity, and efficient feed conversion (Oke *et al.*, 2025). As quail production intensifies, maintaining optimal health and metabolic stability through diet becomes a priority, particularly under conditions that predispose birds to physiological stress (Mehri *et al.*, 2025). Conventional feed additives have improved productivity, growing concerns over antibiotic resistance and residue accumulation have accelerated the search for natural, plant-derived alternatives with functional benefits (Wang *et al.*, 2024).

Among such alternatives, ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) has attracted attention due to its well-documented antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and immunomodulatory properties, largely attributed to bioactive compounds such as gingerols and shogaols (Yucel *et al.*, 2022). Studies in other poultry species, such as broiler chickens, suggest that ginger supplementation can enhance oxidative stability and improve immune competence (Al-Khalaifah *et al.*, 2022). However, despite these promising attributes, there remains a limited body of evidence regarding its specific effects on haematological indices and serum biochemical parameters in Japanese quail. Addressing this gap is essential, as haematological and biochemical profiles will provide critical insights into the physiological status and overall health of quail birds. This present study aims to evaluate the effects of dietary ginger supplementation on haematological parameters and serum biochemical profiles in Japanese quails.

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2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Ethical consideration

All experimental procedures were conducted in strict accordance with the guidelines and approval of the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee at Bayero University Kano, and carried out at the University's Livestock Teaching and Research Farm.

2.2 Study Location

The study was conducted at the Poultry Unit of the Animal Science Livestock Teaching and Research Farm, Bayero University Kano (latitude 11°59'1.59" N; longitude 8°25'24.97" E), Ungogo Local Government Area, Kano State. The area has a tropical dry and wet climate with annual rainfall of 787–960 mm and temperatures between 21°C and 39°C (Olofin 1987).

2.3 Experimental Birds

A total of ninety-six (96) two-week-old unsexed Japanese quail birds were sourced from a reputable breeder in Kano State. Prior to chick placement, the brooding facility was thoroughly cleaned and disinfected to ensure optimal sanitary conditions. Upon arrival, the Japanese quail chicks were individually weighed and immediately provided with drinking water supplemented with glucose to mitigate transportation-induced stress. During the brooding period, thermal comfort was maintained using six 100-W incandescent bulbs as the primary heat source.

2.4 Ginger Preparation

Dried ginger was purchased from Kurmi Market, Kano, and milled to a size of 5mm using a spiced milling machine. The ginger powder was incorporated into formulated diets at four inclusion levels: 0 (control), 0.5, 1.0, and 1.5% respectively.

Table 1. Composition of Experimental Diets for Japanese Quail (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) (g/kg)

Ingredients %	Ginger powder levels (%)			
	0	0.5	1.0	1.5
Maize	39.0	39.0	39.0	39.0
Soybean meal (44%)	41.3	41.3	41.3	41.3
Wheat offal	12.0	11.5	11.0	10.5
Bone meal	3	3	3	3
Salt	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Limestone	2	2	2	2
Lysine	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Methionine	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Vitamin and mineral premix	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Vegetable oil	2	2	2	2
Ginger powder	0	0.5	1.0	1.5
Total	100	100	100	100
Chemical composition g/kg				
Crude protein (%)	23.6	23.5	23.4	23.3
Crude Fiber (%)	4.48	4.44	4.40	4.35
Ether extract	5.37	5.35	5.34	5.32
Calcium	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85
Phosphorus	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.76

2.5 Experimental Design

The experiment was laid out in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) comprising of four dietary treatments with three replicates each, and eight birds per replicate.

2.6 Blood collection and preparation

Blood samples (5 mL per bird) were collected aseptically from the brachial (wing) vein using sterile 5 mL disposable syringes fitted with 23-gauge hypodermic needles (BD Plastipak™, Becton Dickinson, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA). Immediately after collection, each sample was divided into two sterile tubes: 2 mL was dispensed into ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA)-coated tubes (BD Microtainer®, Becton Dickinson, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) for hematological analysis, while the remaining 3 mL was transferred into plain tubes without anticoagulant for serum biochemical assays.

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2.7 Haematological parameters

Hematological parameters were determined immediately after collection. Red blood cell (RBC) and white blood cell (WBC) counts were determined using an improved Neubauer hemocytometer (Marienfeld Superior, Lauda-Königshofen, Germany) following standard dilution protocols as described by Dacie and Lewis (1991). Packed cell volume (PCV) was measured using the microhematocrit method with heparinized capillary tubes (Hawksley & Sons Ltd., Lancing, UK) and a microhematocrit centrifuge (Hawksley Microcentrifuge, UK), as outlined by Bernard *et al.* (2000). Hemoglobin concentration (Hb) was determined via the cyanmethemoglobin method using Drabkin's reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) in accordance with Cole (1986). Erythrocyte indices, including mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), were calculated using standard formulae described by Stockham and Scott (2002).

2.8 Serum Biochemical parameters

Blood in plain tubes was allowed to clot at room temperature (25–27 °C) and subsequently centrifuged at 3,000 rpm for 10 min using a benchtop centrifuge (Eppendorf 5702R, Hamburg, Germany) to obtain serum. The harvested serum was carefully stored at –20 °C pending analysis. Total protein was determined using the Biuret method as described by Doumas (1975), Albumin using dye-binding techniques with bromocresol green as described by Doumas and Birggs (1972) Globulin by difference (Total protein minus Albumin).

2.9 Statistical Analysis

Data were subjected to one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using Genstat version 17. Means were separated using Tukey's procedure (Minitab 17) at 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$).

3. RESULTS

3.1 Haematological parameters

Table 2 shows the haematological parameters of quail birds administered graded inclusion levels of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) powder (0 – 1.5%). Packed Cell Volume (PCV) decreased across treatment groups, from 53.33% in the control group (0%) to 43.67% at 1.5% inclusion; however, this reduction was not statistically significant. Similarly, it was also observed for haemoglobin (Hb), which declined from 17.77 g/dL in the control to 14.50 g/dL at 1.5% inclusion, with no significant effect detected ($p > 0.2292$). Total plasma protein (TPP) values remained relatively stable across all treatment groups offered graded inclusion levels of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) powder, ranging from 5.90% (0%) to 5.43% (1.5%). No statistically significant difference ($p > 0.8979$) was observed. White blood cell (WBC) counts increased with higher levels of ginger powder inclusion, rising from $17.47 \times 10^9/L$ in the control group to $24.53 \times 10^9/L$ at 1.5%. The observed increase was statistically significant ($p < 0.0008$) across the treatment groups.

Red blood cell (RBC) counts showed a decreasing trend from $5.97 \times 10^{12}/L$ (0%) to $4.77 \times 10^{12}/L$ (1.5%), although the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.4572$). Neutrophil percentages varied across treatments, increasing from 24.67% in the control to 33.67% at 0.5%, then declining slightly at higher inclusion levels (29.00% at 1% and 27.67% at 1.5%), with no significant differences ($p > 0.3233$). Lymphocyte (LYMPO) percentages showed a decreasing trend from 74.67% in the control to 65.33% at 0.5% inclusion level, followed by a slight increase at 1% (69.67%) and 1.5% (71.67%), respectively. The observed variations were not statistically significant ($p > 0.2917$). Monocyte (MONO) values were low across all groups, ranging from 0% in the control to 1% at 0.5% and 1%, and 0.33% at 1.5%, with no significant differences ($p > 0.582$) observed across all treatment groups.

Table 2. Effect of dietary supplementation of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) powder at varying levels on Haematological parameters.

Parameters	Ginger powder inclusion level (%)				P value
	0	0.5	1	1.5	
PCV (%)	53.33	47.33	46.67	43.67	0.2367
Hb (g/dL)	17.77	15.53	15.73	14.5	0.2292
TPP (%)	5.9	5.53	5.47	5.43	0.8979
WBC ($\times 10^9/L$)	17.47 ^b	18.80 ^b	20.60 ^b	24.53 ^a	0.0008
RBC ($\times 10^{12}/L$)	5.97	5.4	5.33	4.77	0.4572
NEUTRO (%)	24.67	33.67	29	27.67	0.3233
LYMPO (%)	74.67	65.33	69.67	71.67	0.2917
MONO (%)	0	1	1	0.33	0.582
BAND (%)	0.67	0.55	0.33	0.33	0.7278

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^{a, b,} and ^c Means with the same superscript letters on the same row are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$). PCV: Packed Cell Volume, Hb: Hemoglobin Concentration, TPP: Total Plasma Protein, WBC: White Blood Cell Count, RBC: Red Blood Cell Count, NEUTRO: Neutrophil Percentage, LYMPO: Lymphocyte Percentage, MONO: Monocyte Percentage, BAND: Band Cell Percentage.

3.2 Serum Biochemical parameters

Significant treatment effects were observed for total protein, urea, and alkaline phosphatase, whereas albumin, creatinine, AST, ALT, and glucose remained statistically unaffected ($p > 0.05$) across dietary ginger inclusion levels. Serum albumin (Alb) concentrations showed a decline in values from 1.93 g/dL in the control group (0%) to 1.40 g/dL at 1.5% ginger inclusion, although these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.50$). Similarly, creatinine (Creat) levels varied across treatments, increasing from 0.97 mg/dL in the control group to 1.47 mg/dL at 0.5% inclusion level, before decreasing to 1.03 mg/dL at 1.5%; however, these fluctuations were not significant ($p > 0.27$).

Total Protein concentrations were significantly affected by dietary treatment ($p < 0.009$). The control group recorded the highest value (68.00 g/L), while all ginger supplemented diet groups (0.5–1.5%) showed significantly lower values (55.00–56.67 g/L at 0.5–1% and 54.00 g/L at 1.5%), with no differences among the supplemented groups. Serum urea levels also differed significantly among treatments ($p < 0.04$). The highest value was observed at 0.5% inclusion (4.80 mg/dL), which differed from the lowest value at 1.5% (3.40 mg/dL), while the control (4.10 mg/dL) and 1% inclusion (4.00 mg/dL) groups were intermediate and did not differ significantly from either extreme.

Liver enzyme activities showed variable responses. Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) decreased from 21.33 U/L in the control to 13.33 U/L at 1.5%, though this reduction was not statistically significant ($p > 0.11$). Alanine aminotransferase (ALT) values remained relatively stable across treatments (17.67–20.67 U/L), with no significant differences detected ($p > 0.79$). Alkaline phosphatase (ALP) activity was significantly influenced by ginger supplementation ($p < 0.02$). The highest value was recorded at 1.5% inclusion (12.00 U/L), which differed from the lowest value at 0.5% (7.00 U/L), while the control (10.67 U/L) and 1% ginger inclusion (10.33 U/L) groups were intermediate and statistically comparable. Serum glucose concentrations showed a decreasing numerical trend with increasing ginger inclusion, from 202 mg/dL in the control to 163.33 mg/dL at 1.5%, but this variation was not statistically significant ($p > 0.52$).

Table 3. Effect of dietary supplementation of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) powder at varying levels on serum biochemical parameters.

Parameters	Ginger powder inclusion level (%)				P value
	0	0.5	1	1.5	
Alb g/dl	1.93	1.43	1.53	1.4	0.50
Creat mg/dl	0.97	1.47	1.13	1.03	0.27
Protein g/l	68.00 ^a	55.00 ^b	56.67 ^b	54.00 ^b	0.009
Urea mg/dl	4.10 ^{ab}	4.80 ^a	4.00 ^{ab}	3.40 ^b	0.041
AST u/l	21.33	17	18	13.33	0.11
ALT u/l	20.67	20.67	17.67	20	0.79
ALP u/l	10.67 ^{ab}	7.00 ^b	10.33 ^{ab}	12.00 ^a	0.02
Glucose Md/gl	202	188.67	196	163.33	0.52
Alb g/dl	1.93	1.43	1.53	1.4	0.50
Creat mg/dl	0.97	1.47	1.13	1.03	0.27

^{a, b,} and ^c Means with the same superscript letters on the same row are not significantly different ($p > 0.05$). Alb: Albumin, Creat: Creatinine, Protein: Total Protein, Urea: Urea, AST: Aspartate Aminotransferase, ALT: Alanine Aminotransferase, ALP: Alkaline Phosphatase, Glucose: Blood Glucose Level, Alb: Albumin, Creat: Creatinine.

4. DISCUSSION

The findings from this study indicate that ginger supplementation elicited effects on haematological indices of Japanese quail birds, with statistically significant values observed only in white blood cell (WBC) counts. This could be due to the immunostimulatory effect of ginger, consistent with its well-documented bioactive compounds, including gingerols and shogaols, which possess antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties (Yucel *et al.*, 2022). The observed rise in WBC may reflect enhanced immune surveillance of innate immune responses, a phenomenon widely reported in poultry receiving phyto-genic supplements. This study corroborates the findings of (Kairalla *et al.*, 2022) who reported that ginger powder supplementation had significant effect on the white blood cell (WBC) counts of broiler chickens.

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The dietary intake of ginger had significant effects on biochemical markers of Japanese quails as far as serum levels were concerned. Total protein level, urea, and ALP activity were significantly higher in the ginger diets compared to the control group. Since we have found that protein levels change significantly regardless of the type of ginger diet consumed, we can safely conclude that there is an alteration in protein metabolism. Ginger, as a regulator of liver proteins, might be mediated by bioactive compounds abundant in ginger, such as gingerols and shogaols, which exhibit antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. This observation corroborates previous research by Al-Khalaifah *et al.* (2022), who reported that dietary inclusion of ginger significantly increased total protein (TP) levels in poultry blood serum.

Urea levels showed a remarkable effect, irrespective of inclusion level, with the highest levels of inclusion associated with lower urea levels than medium-level inclusions. This suggests that ginger use may affect nitrogen metabolism pathways in a dose-dependent manner. Lower levels of urea due to high inclusions could be attributed to enhanced protein metabolism or to protein breakdown. This study is not in tandem with the report by Manaa *et al.* (2024), who found that dietary inclusion of ginger did not affect blood biochemical parameters.

A significant difference in Alkaline phosphatase enzyme activity was observed, with the high inclusion group exhibiting greater activity than the low inclusion group. This finding indicates potential alterations in hepatic function, as ALP activity is commonly associated with liver function. Agbalaya *et al.* (2024) in his study reported that a blend of ginger and turmeric had a significant effect on ALP of broiler chickens.

5. CONCLUSION

Dietary inclusion of ginger regulated key haematological and biochemical indices in Japanese quails. The observed responses in the research occurred without detrimental disruption of core physiological parameters hence, supporting ginger's efficacy as a functional phyto-genic additive for enhancing health status and metabolic efficiency in quail production systems.

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